

Development of a marketing strategy for the enterprise “Farovon-uz”

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Abstract: This article examines the presence of a strategy, constant analysis of the existing strategy, analysis of the degree of its compliance with current market conditions, and the emergence of new strong competitors.

Key words: Enterprises, strategy, competition, market, product, demand, analysis.

“Strategic management is the process of making and implementing strategic decisions, the central element of which is strategic choice based on comparing the enterprise’s own resource potential with the opportunities and threats of the external environment in which it operates. Strategy can be seen as the primary link between what an organization wants to achieve—its goals—and the course of action chosen to achieve those goals.

The essence of strategic management lies in answering three critical questions:

1. What is the current situation of the organization?
2. What position would it like to be in three, five, ten years?
3. How to achieve the desired position?

Strategic management is based on strategic decisions. Strategic decisions are management decisions that:

- 1) are future-oriented and lay the foundation for making operational management decisions;
- 2) are associated with significant uncertainty, since they take into account external factors affecting the organization;
- 3) involve significant resources and can have serious, long-term consequences for the organization.

The concept of “planning” includes defining goals and ways to achieve them. The planning process goes through four stages:

- development of common goals;
- determination of specific, detailed goals for a given, relatively short period of time (2,5,10 years);
- determination of ways and means to achieve them;
- monitoring the achievement of set goals by comparing planned indicators with actual ones.

The Farovon-uz supermarket is distinguished by a personal approach to each client and a high level of service: our specialists will always help with the choice, and gastronomic department experts will help with delicacies and create a menu for the festive table.

Our interiors are designed in such a way that a person immediately finds himself in a special atmosphere of comfort. Supermarket “Farovon-uz” is one of the largest supermarkets in Samarkand. Despite the fact that grocery stores and supermarkets are represented in Samarkand in huge quantities, what distinguishes us from dozens of other respected and well-known brands is, first of all, our uniqueness.

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“Farovon-uz” is quite successfully fighting for its market share, mainly due to the experience of sellers and relatively low prices for goods.

From current practice it follows that the most important assessment indicators that are widely used are:

- Trade turnover
- Gross profit
- Conditionally net profit
- Profit after paying interest on loans and credits
- Profit after taxes

All data given below are rounded (approximate).

Main economic indicators

Indicators	Years		
	2021	2022	2023
Trade turnover (billion soums)	12.56	12.62	12.71
Gross profit (million soums)	340	370	400
Conditional net profit (million soums)	297	327	357
Profit after interest on loans and credits (million soums)	210	287	310
Profit after taxes (million soums)	164	233	262
Net profit (million soums)	122	206	226
Average annual cost of open pension fund (million soums)	14.6	16.4	19
Average annual stock of goods in warehouses (million soums)	810	860	710
Average number of workers (persons)	6	10	15

The table shows that in general the enterprise operates efficiently. A comparison of key indicators over the years shows that store profits are steadily increasing, although the rate of profit growth in the last year has decreased slightly due to an increase in the number of retail outlets and, accordingly, the costs of their maintenance. This is also due to the factor of enormous external competition from “Orion”, “Korzinka”, “Halol”.

Despite such external factors as competition, the store is increasing the number of its outlets in the city.

Also, the drop in profit growth rates is associated with an increase in the number of employees, both managers and ordinary personnel. This resulted in additional wage costs.

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An increase in the average annual cost of goods in warehouses indicates that warehouses are overloaded, since, in fact, the warehouses themselves are not increasing. The director is actively importing new goods, and these goods are almost always either of higher quality, or more inexpensive, or more advanced and new. This trend leads to cluttering of warehouses, since sellers are interested in selling the most liquid goods, and such goods are the most liquid. As a result, a huge amount of “unliquid” remains in warehouses. All these goods, in essence, simply physically interfere with sales, and plus they are frozen money. It is necessary to approach this issue competently.

Our store is a supermarket. We will begin the analysis by examining the composition of the store’s staff, the number of employees and their positions, all of which we will display in a diagram.

The director assigns only part of his powers to the merchandise manager, in terms of personnel management, as well as in certain functions to the chief accountant and salespeople. On the one hand, such a policy is very effective in the sense that the director (who is also the owner) personally controls the entire work process. This is all the more necessary for him, since he is the owner of this trade organization, and is more interested in its effective work than anyone else.

Also, in practice, almost all store employees perform functions that are not inherent in their position. For example: a cashier-operator, in addition to being a credit inspector, is engaged in filling out documents such as invoices, invoices, bills; sales consultants act as loaders. In general, almost all employees perform cross-functional functions; this strategy or policy is used in almost all small sales organizations. This is due to the fact that such a structure is less expensive and easier to manage.

The biggest advantages of this structure are:

- it does not require large financial costs for maintaining a large staff;
- it does not require additional costs for maintaining a large management apparatus over these personnel;
- in such an organization there is almost always a “good atmosphere”, in the sense that the director is the immediate superior, and everyone else is equal;
- a unique corporate culture that does not rely on any strict rules of behavior, etc.
- the staff has a lot of experience;
- staff versatility.

The disadvantages are the following:

- a very large load on the director himself;
- workload of other personnel;
- shortcomings in performing one's duties due to distraction by others.

From the analysis of the control system, we conclude that, despite the fact that a simple control scheme is the least expensive, there are problems that require immediate solutions. There are hidden reserves that can be realized with the right approach.

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The supermarket director, due to his workload with operational and other issues, will not pay due attention to strategic planning issues.

In modern trade organizations, the marketing strategy is especially important in achieving their goals, and especially the goal of increasing profitability, profitability and increasing turnover. This strategy, as a rule, reflects the correct course for promoting goods on the market, segments the market, studies consumer tastes, preferences, etc.

The marketing strategy includes three components:

- 1.Strategy for selecting the target market (segmentation).
- 2.Strategy for positioning and creating competitive advantage.
- 3.strategy for the existence of a product (brand) is a mix strategy, which consists of complex measures relating to the product, price, promotion, distribution.

Let's look at which segments our supermarket is targeting.

Taking into account the peculiarities of the assortment policy, the main buyers in the Farovon - uz supermarket will be:

1. people with average incomes who count on relatively inexpensive and high-quality domestically produced goods: 65%;
2. since the supermarket has a well-developed cashless payment system, according to transfers, a large share of customers are various organizations financed from the State budget: 18%;
3. regular customers 12%;
4. and others: 5%.

For effective operation, an enterprise needs not only the presence of a strategy, but also a constant analysis of the existing strategy, an analysis of the degree of its compliance with the current market conditions. Because without this it is impossible to operate successfully or maintain a stable competitive advantage, which in modern market conditions is extremely important for any enterprise.

After the work done regarding the analysis of the current strategy of the Farovon - uz supermarket, the following conclusions can be drawn.

It should be noted that the current enterprise strategy is rather ineffective, as evidenced by the results of strategy diagnostics. The following facts indicate this:

1. The growth rate of trade turnover is very low;
2. Also, expansion of retail space is slow;
3. Due to the lack of any advertising and the emergence of new strong competitors, the Farovon - uz supermarket is losing a large number of customers.
4. An incorrect management system hinders economic development due to the distraction of the store director to solve operational and other problems.

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